

Exploring Inner Potential: Navigating Self-Discovery

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Summary

This presentation centers on the significance of self-discovery in today's context, led by Pramila Thapa, PhD, founder of Life Skill Education in Nepal. It aims to foster discussions and provide actionable insights for personal enrichment. Phil Johnson, CEO of the Master of Business Leadership program, brings 31 years of success, emphasizing emotional intelligence and leadership. Michael Rada discusses the "Power of Touch" in self-discovery within INDUSTRY 5.0. Social media's impact on self-esteem is highlighted. Pat Armitstead's experience with the "tall poppy syndrome" underscores obstacles. Collectively, these perspectives explore self-discovery's importance and challenges, offering a holistic view of personal growth.

The primary objective of this topic is to examine its significance in the contemporary context, stimulate meaningful discussions, and provide actionable insights for enriching self-discovery.

I am Pramila Thapa, PhD the founder of Life Skill Education in Nepal. My work centers on the topic of self-discovery. The journey of self-discovery forms a profound cornerstone of my experiences. It involves comprehending our potential, purpose, and growth. Self-discovery delves into our values, emotions, and aspirations. Through dimensions like self-awareness, development, mastery, and actualization, we unveil layers of our identity. Each aspect contributes significantly to personal growth. Yet, challenges like autosuggestion, societal pressures, family expectations, and peer influences can hinder this process. Despite obstacles, the intricate nature of self-discovery encourages further exploration, particularly within today's societal context.

I'm Phil Johnson, Founder and CEO of the Master of Business Leadership program. With 31 years of success, our program impacts personal, career, and corporate growth. Alumni span worldwide, including the US, Canada, UK, Europe, Japan, and more. Our focus on emotional intelligence, leadership, and higher consciousness fosters success. Born in Ontario, Canada, I overcame challenges including dyslexia. Early jobs shaped my journey, fueled by a decision to thrive after personal loss. Transitioning from corporate to education, I realized that wealth and success require a holistic approach.

MICHAEL RADA, HUMAN

Q1: The self-discovery is connecting with delivery of palpable results in which the possibility to be touched is very important. Within INDUSTRY 5.0 we call this the POWER OF TOUCH and it is one of the most important tools on the construction site of WASTELESS WORLD. The delivered result must not be (and frequently is not) perfect, but represents the “discovery” of person’s deepest skills and pride on delivered result.

Q2: The main factor is the distrust in personal ability TO DO. This can be encouraged by the environment in which the person grow-up, study and live and significant impact have SOCIAL MEDIA that simplify the “life” on LIKES and DISLIKES and at the same time pretend to be real, and not only virtual. A number of DISLIKES after unperfected result delivered can discouraged the author from delivering next result and can lead to self-underrating, and discovery of uselessness, frequently very opposite I the reality, but the people refuse to continue in the work and become lethargic, remaining on DGITAL

Pat Armitstead, Thank you for the invitation to participate. You inquired about hindrances to self-discovery. The "tall poppy syndrome" prevalent in Australia and New Zealand hindered my journey due to self-doubt. Overcoming this, I cultivated vigilance, personal growth, and firm boundaries to protect my light

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